

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3871380
CZU 371.3

INTERACTIVE TEACHING

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Received: 04. 22. 2020

Accepted: 05. 24. 2020

Abstract. Interactive teaching is an epitomic strategy that engages as many learners as possible, consequently encouraging the gratification of learning, research methods and heuristic. The entertainment process tends to motivate learning, expands communicative skills, stimulates critical thinking and brings academic contentment. Edutainment is designed to educate through entertainment. Recurrently it encompasses content intended to teach but has concomitant entertainment value. It has been produced by academia, corporations, governments, and other establishments in various countries to distribute information in classrooms and/or via television, radio, media, CMCs etc. Interactive teaching strategy focuses on the transition from passive learners to more active ones, facilitating maximum involvement during lectures, thus an academic metamorphosis takes place - info recipients are becoming completely implied peers of the academic affair. Moreover, it is the methodology of combining the practices of teaching and the form of game to enchant the students and make the utmost of the games operational effect to help education.

Keywords: *edutainment, epidemic boredom, eureka effect, gamification, ludus, playfulness.*

Rezumat. Predarea interactivă este o strategie indispensabilă, care implică cât mai mulți cursanți, încurajând, în consecință, plăcerea de a învăța, metodele de cercetare și euristica. Procesul interactiv tinde să motiveze învățarea, extinde abilitățile comunicative, stimulează gândirea critică și aduce satisfacții academice. Educația prin divertisment este concepută pentru a ghida prin intermediul elementelor umoristice/de joacă. În mod repetat, aceasta cuprinde un conținut menit să învețe, dar având și o valoare concomitentă de divertisment, fiind produsă de mediul academic, corporații, guverne și alte instituții din diferite țări pentru a distribui informații în sălile de clasă și / sau prin televiziune, radio, media, comunicare mediată de calculator etc. Strategia de predare interactivă se concentrează pe trecerea de la cursanții pasivi la cei activi, facilitează implicarea maximă în timpul prelegerilor, astfel are loc o metamorfoză academică - destinatarii de cunoștințe devin membri (expeditori) implicați în afacerea academică. Mai mult decât atât, este metodologia combinării practicilor de predare și a jocului pentru a-i încânta pe studenți și pentru o maximă operare a ingredientului umoristic privind îmbunătățirea învățării.

Cuvinte-cheie: *educație prin divertisment, efect eureka, element jucăuș, joc, ludus.*

Introduction

“Society needs humour, not just for entertainment. In the current business world, humor is considered to be so important that companies may hire humor consultants. Humor can be used to criticize without alienating, to defuse tension or anxiety, to introduce new ideas, to bond teams, ease relationships and elicit cooperation”[1].

Research in humour has revealed a variety of entertainment types, also, its cause and effect on people and situational environment. In fact, humour occurs in a welcoming and amiable atmosphere, thus contributing to a better understanding, perception, and motivation of the acquired subject. In particular, being a desirable and major key element in teaching and learning, humour in demand for naturalness and effectiveness, in fact adds value to any beginnings and discoveries in the scientific world.

Scola Ludus

The fascination for combining education with entertainment, especially in order to alleviate learning more pleasant, has existed for centuries. Thus in ancient Roman and Greek culture, the term ludus has several annotations within semantic field of: play, games, sport, training [2]. Latin lyric often scrutinizes the concept of ludus as a playfulness. As well as “Scola Ludus -school as play- concept, which proposes pedagogy with dramatic or delightful elements” [3]. Among the first, who mentioned playfulness in education has been Plato. He suggested that “intellectual play could provide a stimulus to understanding” [4]. Aristotle noted the “historical connection between leisure and the growth of learning”[5]. If we jump from ancient to the time of Renaissance and Illumination, pioneers like: Spencer (1552-1599), Bacon (1561-1626), Komensky (1592-1670), Rousseau (1712-1778), Pestalozzi (1746-1827) pointed out that “learners acquire knowledge most efficiently in a pleasant, playful environment, moreover emphasizing the function of a play as pedagogically effective activity” [6].

Komensky – the father of modern education, remembered mainly for his innovations in methods of teaching, especially languages considered that: “school is the manufactory of humanity”; “Much can be learned in play that will afterwards be of use when circumstances demand it”; “Let the main object...to seek and to find a method of instruction, by which teachers may teach less, but learners learn more” [7]. Plato proposed to “regulate play for social ends; he seemed to suggest that intellectual play in some form, as demonstrated in the dialectical banter of Socrates, could provide a stimulus to understanding” [4].

Gamification

Many pioneers in the field of psychology, including Jean Piaget (1962), Carl Jung (1987) and Lev Vygotsky (2011) have considered playfulness salient for human development and using various research methods to prove their theories[8]. Different forms of play, whether it is physical or mental, have determined cognitive abilities in individuals. Consequently, the old traditional way of learning has to be refashioned into a modern one as a game based learning (GBL) and gamification.

The game based learning is an educational approach to stimulate students to learn by using game components in learning environments. The aim of gamification is to maximize amusement and commitment through attracting the interest of learners and motivating them to continue learning. Game-based learning (GBL) delineates learning outcomes, nevertheless it is destined to balance subject matter with gameplay and the potential of the player to commit, and apply the subject matter to the real environment. “In

a successful game-based learning environment, choosing actions, experiencing consequences, and working toward goals allows players to make mistakes through experimentation in a risk-free environment” [9].

University epidemic boredom

A 2013 Gallup poll “Bored out of their Minds” of 500.000 students suggests that almost 60% of students find at least half their lectures boring, with about 30% claiming to find most or all of their lectures boring.

The most vivid examples are: daydreaming (75%), doodling (66%), chatting to friends (50%), sending texts (45%), and passing notes to friends (38%). Over a quarter of students tend to leave the lecture at the mid-session break. “This ‘class cutting’ is potentially the most serious consequence, since previous research has shown a link between attendance and grades.”

Similarly a boredom questionnaire “TUM Epidemic classroom boredom” of 71 students from three faculties from Technical University of Moldova suggests that:

- 39.4% are sometimes bored during classes, 26.7%- are rarely bored, 20% -are often bored
- Missing boring classes: 52%- never, 37%- rarely, 21% -often
- Finding university boring: 48% -never, 39%-rarely
- Caring teachers: 35% -often, 24%-sometimes
- Boring homework: 34%- rarely, 32.4% - sometimes
- Monotonous, useless subjects-25.35%, tedious teachers-20%, boring methods-17%
- The most boring subjects: Physics and Math- 51%
- Dull homework: 30% -too much h/w, 15%- do not consider it dull
- Recommendations: 57.14% -jokes, games, interactivity, 12.6- change methods

Boredom prevention

One of the easiest and most effective paths to prevent boredom is to have fun ourselves. If we are having a good time, likely our students have fun too. Emotional Contagious Yale University research shows that if we put our students in a good mood they’ll learn more.

The sudden understanding of “AHA” moments or eureka effect promote learning by increasing dopamine, endorphins and oxygen in the brain, resulting in flashes of clarity being like a spring for innovative ideas and breakthrough performances. Other far-reaching approaches like: challenging students and getting them out of their comfort zone; storytelling is a well-documented engagement strategy and it was the primary way we learned before we started writing things down; flexible sitting which uses brain breaks to help break up the day and refocus attention; providing choice to learners or taking the initiative leads to more stimulation and curiosity; connecting teaching to real life proves the relationship between learning goals and real situational environment.

Conclusion

The major fact concerning interactive teaching is about instructing the learners in a way they are actively involved within the learning process. Therefore, in pursue for the effective teaching, humour and playfulness constitute the best renovator, a stress buster also a fear and anxiety killer, an ice-breaker, moreover, a grantor to think out of the box

and enhance learning, and nonetheless is a productive fun ingredient to engage students and stimulate learning. Thus, it is desirable to organize lessons into easily assimilated steps to make learning gradual, cumulative and pleasant.

References:

1. Oliviero Stock and Carlo Strapparava, ITC-irst, Istituto per la Ricerca Scientifica e Tecnologica, I-38050 Trento, Italy,113(1).
2. Oxford Latin Dictionary (1985). (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1048–1049).
3. Comenius, J. A. (1896). Great Didactica of John Amos Comenius. New York: Russell & Russell
4. Plato (360 B.C.). The Republic: Book VI. Free eBooks by project Gutenberg: Retrieved: <http://www.gutenberg.org/files/1497/1497-h/1497-h.htm>.
5. Aristotle (2013). Politics. Chicago: The University Chicago Press.
6. Pestalozzi, J. H. (1894). How Gertrude teaches her children. London: Swan Sonnenschein.
7. Komensky, J. A. (1913). Ve kere Spisy Jana Amusa Komenského Didactica Magna. Brno: NUSJUNM
8. Vygotskij, L. S. (2011). Vorlesungen über Psychologie [Lectures on Psychology]. Berlin: Lehmanns Media.
9. Walz, S. P., Deterding, S. (2014). The gameful world: Approaches, issues, applications. Cambridge: MIT Press. Journal of Baltic Science Education, 14 (1), 121-130.
10. Pavlus, J. (2010). The game of life. Scientific American, 303, 43–44.
11. D'Angour, A. (2013). Plato and play, taking education seriously in Ancient Greece. American Journal of Play, 5 (3), 293-307.
12. Pešakovič, D., Flogie, A., Aberšek, B. (2014). Development and evaluation of a competence-based teaching process for science and technology education. Journal of Baltic Science Education, 13 (5), 740-755.